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Chemical Investigation of the Fruits of *Voacanga grandifolia* (Miq.) Rolfe

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Manuscript received 10 August 1973; accepted 2 November 1973

OCCURRENCE of alkaloids in *Voacanga* species¹ encouraged us to chemically examine the different parts of a new *Voacanga* plant, *Voacanga grandifolia* (Miq.) Rolfe² (*Apocynaceae*). *V. grandifolia*, a native of Java, is a deciduous erect shrub. It is cultivated in the Indian Gardens. Phytochemical investigation for the first time of the fruits of *Voacanga grandifolia* has revealed the presence of three indole alkaloids and two neutral components. In the present communication we report their isolation and characterization.

Air-dried milled fruits (1 kg) were extracted with alcohol. The extract was concentrated under reduced pressure and fractionated into basic and non-basic constituents by churning with 5% aq. citric acid followed by filtration. The aq. citrate containing the basic components was extracted with CHCl_3 (CSC), washed with NH_4OH , dried and concentrated. The remaining aq. citrate was basified with NH_4OH , extracted with CHCl_3 (SB), washed with H_2O , dried and concentrated. Both the CSC and SB fractions were chromatographed over alumina (Brockmann activity¹) separately. The petrol (b. p. $60^\circ\text{-}80^\circ$)- C_6H_6 (1:1) eluate of the CSC fraction yielded a solid, purified as hydrochloride (15 mg), m. p. 192° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -370^\circ$ (MeOH). The parent alkaloid, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ (M^+ 336) was generated as an amorph. solid by basification of the hydrochloride with NH_4OH . Its uv and ir spectra indicate the presence of a β -anilinomethacrylate chromophore^{1,2} and the mass spectrum is typical of a vincadifformine-type alkaloid⁴. The identity of the alkaloid with (-) tabersonine^{5,6} was finally established by comparison with an authentic sample. Chromatography of the SB fraction afforded a solid from the C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (4:1) eluate. The solid on several crystallizations from MeOH- CHCl_3 furnished a crystalline compound (100 mg), $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ (M^+ 718), m. p. 303° (dec.) $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} -311^\circ$ (CHCl_3). This was identified as vobtusine^{7,8} (uv, ir, MS, m. m. p. and Co-tlc with an authentic sample). Elution of the above chromatogram with C_6H_6 - CHCl_3 (3:1) yielded the other alkaloid (40 mg), crystallized from MeOH- CHCl_3 , $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ (M^+ 352), m. p. 242° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +20^\circ$ (EtOH). It was finally characterized as rhazine^{9,10} by comparison (m. m. p., Co-tlc, uv, ir and MS) with an authentic sample.

The non-basic fraction was chromatographed over silica gel G. The petrol eluate gave a solid (30 mg), crystallized from MeOH, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$ (M^+ 468), m. p. 214° , $[\alpha]_{\text{D}} +27.2^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It was characterized as lupeol-acetate by comparison with an authentic sample

(m. m. p., superimposable ir and Co-tlc in silica gel G impregnated with AgNO_3 solution). The petrol- C_6H_6 (1:1) eluate yielded β -sitosterol, m. p. 136° ; acetate, m. p. 124° (identified by m. m. p., Co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra with an authentic sample).

Acknowledgment

We thank Dr. B. C. Das, Gif-sur-Yvette, France for MS and Dr. S. C. Pakrashi, I. I. E. M., Calcutta for ir spectra. B. N. D. is thankful to CSIR (India) for financial assistance.

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Uranyl 12-Molybdophosphate

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Manuscript received 25 April 1973; accepted 1 November 1973

THISTLETHWAITE has synthesized 12-Molybdophosphates of a number of metal ions by neutralization reaction between metal oxides or metal carbonates and 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.^{1,2} Following this method of synthesis 12-Molybdophosphate of Uranyl Cation has been prepared by the reaction between Uranyl Carbonate and 12-Molybdophosphoric acid.